

Studies on Hydrazones, Semicarbazones, Thiosemicarbazones and Oximes as Ligands. Part-I. Some Divalent Metal Complexes of Benzoin Phenylhydrazone and Thiosemicarbazone

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A number of complexes of the composition ML_2X_2 where M(II) is Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd; X is Cl^- , NO_3^- , NCS^- except the perchlorate complexes which are of the formula $(ML_2)X_2$ where X is ClO_4^- and L is benzoin phenylhydrazone, and also complexes of the type ML'_2Cl_2 and ML''_2 , where M(II) is Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd; L' is benzoin thiosemicarbazone and L'' is the anion of L', have been synthesised. These are characterised on the basis of analytical, conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Schiff bases have drawn considerable attention since such ligands dominate the area of higher coordination polyhedra in scope, number and also from kinetic and thermodynamic stability point of view. Particularly, the compact nature of polydentate Schiff bases make them more effective in attaining high coordination structure. Complexation behaviour of bi-, tri- and tetradentate Schiff bases have been reported¹. Thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones have attracted much attention due to their various biological activities². Since the discovery of their antitubercular activity by Domagk *et al.*³, it was found that some drugs have increased activity when administered as metal complexes⁴ and a number of metal chelate were found to inhibit tumour growth⁵. In the treatment of cancer, the active species is a metal chelate of thiosemicarbazone⁶. Following the work of Mashima⁷ coordination chemists have taken greater interest in thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones as potential ligands.

The present investigation reports the synthesis and characterisation of some divalent metal com-

plexes of benzoin phenylhydrazone and thiosemicarbazone.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have the composition ML_2X_2 or $(ML_2)Y_2$ where M(II) is Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Cd; L is benzoin phenyl hydrazone and thiosemicarbazone; X is Cl^- , NO_3^- or NCS^- , and Y is ClO_4^- . Also complexes of the composition ML''_2 , where L'' is the anion of benzoin thiosemicarbazone, have been synthesised. Compounds have fairly low melting points excepting the perchlorate complexes and are soluble in common organic solvents. Acetone solution of the complexes show low molar conductance values indicating non-electrolytic nature of the compounds. However, the perchlorate complexes have molar conductance values of the order of $170-180 \Omega^{-1} cm^2$, characteristic of compounds having 1 : 2 electrolytes. Magnetic moments of the complexes are indicative of spin-free octahedral environment while the moments of nickel and copper perchlorate complexes indicate tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral environment.

TABLE I—COMPLEXES OF BENZOIN PHENYLHYDRAZONE AND THIOSEMICARBAZONE

Compd / (M p ^o C, Colour)	λ_{M} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % Found/(Calc'd).	
			Metal	Halogen
(A) Complexes of benzoïn phenylhydrazone :				
CoL ₂ Cl ₂ (108, Pink)	10.5	4.9	7.83 (8.02)	9.33 (9.65)
NiL ₂ Cl ₂ (124, Green)	9.8	2.9	7.68 (7.99)	9.15 (9.66)
CuL ₂ Cl ₂ (85, Green)	14.3	1.79	8.88 (8.59)	9.24 (9.59)
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂ (128, White)	18.2	—	8.94 (8.82)	9.96 (9.57)
CdL ₂ Cl ₂ (145, White)	16.5	—	13.92 (14.26)	9.31 (8.99)
CoL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (129, Orange)	11.4	5.1	7.13 (7.48)	—
NiL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (132, Green)	15.3	3.1	7.20 (7.45)	—
CuL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (125, Green)	16.8	1.8	7.71 (8.02)	—
ZnL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (135, White)	14.5	—	7.81 (8.23)	—
CdL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (126, White)	11.8	—	13.25 (13.36)	—
NiL ₂ (NCS) ₂ (120, Green)	18.4	2.95	7.03 (7.53)	—
CuL ₂ (NCS) ₂ (146, Green)	12.5	1.82	8.42 (8.10)	—
ZnL ₂ (NCS) ₂ (118, White)	17.6	—	8.23 (8.31)	—
(NiL ₂)(ClO ₄) ₂ (200, Green)	186	3.6	6.31 (6.81)	—
(CuL ₂)(ClO ₄) ₂ (200, Blue)	178	2.1	7.21 (7.33)	—
(ZnL ₂)(ClO ₄) ₂ (200, White)	165	—	7.41 (7.52)	—
(B) Complexes of benzoïn thiosemicarbazone :				
CoL ₂ Cl ₂ (168, Pink)	10.8	4.9	8.13 (8.41)	10.33 (10.12)
NiL ₂ Cl ₂ (186, Green)	8.6	2.9	8.29 (8.38)	9.98 (10.12)
CuL ₂ Cl ₂ (174, Green)	11.2	1.79	8.62 (9.01)	10.46 (10.05)
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂ (161, White)	6.4	—	8.83 (9.25)	10.38 (10.03)
CdL ₂ Cl ₂ (155, White)	8.8	—	14.56 (14.91)	9.62 (9.40)
CoL ₂ ² (172, Pink)	8.1	4.95	9.21 (9.40)	—
NiL ₂ ² (181, Green)	10.5	2.98	9.25 (9.36)	—
CuL ₂ ² (165, Green)	12.4	1.8	9.83 (10.06)	—
ZnL ₂ ² (154, White)	8.4	—	10.21 (10.32)	—
CdL ₂ ² (166, White)	9.8	—	16.48 (16.52)	—

Infrared spectra of benzoïn phenylhydrazone has main absorption bands⁸ at 3 400 (OH), 3 350 (NH), 1 660 (C=N), 1 575 (δ NH), 1 060 (C—O) cm^{-1} . In the complexes, ν_{OH} band remains unaffected whereas $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ shifts, to lower frequency region and other characteristic bands in the fingerprint region are modified. Thus the ligand behaves in a bidentate manner in the complexes coordinating through the azomethine nitrogen and hydroxyl-oxygen atoms. In the perchlorate complexes, a broad band around 1 100 cm^{-1} indicates the ionic nature of the perchlorate group. Ir spectra of benzoïn thiosemicarbazone has main absorption bands at 3 420 (OH), 3 320 (NH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 575 (δ OH) and 790 (C=S) cm^{-1} . In ML_2Cl_2 type complexes, ν_{NH} band remains almost unaffected. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band invariably shifts to lower frequency region around 1 600 cm^{-1} , where as $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ occurs around 750 cm^{-1} . Thus, in these complexes, the ligand coordinates in a bidentate manner through the azomethine nitrogen and thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms. In case of ML_2^2 type complexes, in addition to the shifting of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ frequencies, ν_{OH} and δ_{OH} modes disappear as the OH group is deprotonated and oxygen is bonded to the metal ion. Hence, in these complexes the ligand behaves as tridentate.

In the visible electronic spectra, the Co^{II} complexes show the main bands around 18.8–19.1 kK with a shoulder on the high frequency side. The band is attributable⁹ to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition; the shoulder being the consequence of splitting due to spin-orbit coupling. Thus, the band position, intensity and magnetic moment values support the octahedral stereochemistry of the compounds. The Ni^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 9.6, 13.6–13.7 and 24.8 kK assignable¹⁰ to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, suggesting octahedral stereochemistry in conformity with their magnetic moment values. In case of Cu^{II} complexes, one broad band is observed at 13.5–14.0 kK region suggesting a distorted octahedral configuration¹¹ of these complexes. Though three transitions ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2A_1(\nu_1)$; ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\nu_2)$; ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2E(\nu_3)$ are expected in Cu^{II} complexes of D_{2h} symmetry due to Jahn-Teller distortion,

they are often very close in energy and give rise to single broad band. All the zinc and cadmium complexes (excepting perchlorate) have probably octahedral geometry, which is in consonance with their analytical conductance and infrared spectral data. The perchlorate complexes of nickel and copper have presumably a tetrahedral configuration as intense bands are observed at 15.0 ($\epsilon = 190$) and 8.3 ($\epsilon = 45$) kK region for the nickel and copper complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Benzoin phenylhydrazone and thiosemicarbazone were prepared by a known method¹². Ethanol solution of divalent metal salts were refluxed with ethanol solution of the ligand in 1 : 2 proportions for 30–60 min. Volume of the solution was then reduced and on cooling the solutions overnight, crystalline compounds separated out. In some cases, addition of carbon tetrachloride was necessary to precipitate out the complexes. ML_2 type complexes were prepared by reacting the metal acetates with the ligand in 1 : 2 proportion in ethanol medium. Compounds were filtered under suction, washed with small quantity of ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Metal ions, chloride and thiocyanate were estimated by standard gravimetric procedures. Conductance of the complexes was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution using a Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic measurement on solid specimens

was made by Gouy method at 25° using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as calibrant. Infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (in $10^{-2} M CCl_4$) on a Hilger-Watt UV-speck spectrophotometer.

References

1. B. B. MOHAPATRA, S. GURU and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *Acta Chim.*, 1977, **94**, 191; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2291; 1978, **40**, 1178; C. D. RAO, S. GURU and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 1195.
2. H. G. PETERING, H. H. BUSKIRK and G. E. UNDERWOOD, *Cancer Res.*, 1964, **64**, 367.
3. G. DOMAGK, R. SEHENISCH, F. MIERZSCH and H. SCHIMDT, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1946, **33**, 315.
4. D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **72**, 203.
5. F. P. DWYER, E. MAYHEW, E. M. F. ROE and A. SCHILMAN, *Br. J. Cancer*, 1965, **19**, 195.
6. J. A. CRIM and H. G. PETERING, *Cancer Res.*, 1967, **27**, 1278; H. G. PETERING and G. J. VANGEISSEN, "The Biochemistry of Copper", Academic, New York, 1966, p. 197.
7. M. MASHIMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1964, **37**, 974.
8. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
10. B. N. FIGGIS, "An Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley-Eastern, New Delhi, 1976.
11. C. A. AGAMBER and K. G. ORREL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 897.
12. A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1971.

